

**THE ROLE OF THE SPOKESPERSON
IN BUILDING REPUTATION
PERSONALITY TRAITS OF THE M.A.I.
(MINISTRY OF HOME AFFAIRS) SPOKESPERSON**

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Review of the work

*The Spokesperson's Personality. Communication styles,
charisma, performance,*
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Abstract

Communication is an essential component of coexistence in a community. People adapt to social norms, establish relationships and seek to satisfy their main needs based on harmonizing norms with their own beliefs. By communication we mean the process of transmitting and receiving the message.

Further on, communication is an essential component of an organization's success, whether private or legal entity. In this context, the role of the spokesperson becomes crucial in ensuring effective communication between the organization and its audience. This article focuses on identifying the communication characteristics of spokespersons and how these characteristics influence organizational communication and their performance in this position.

The representation of public institutions and the provision of data and information, ex officio or upon request, is regulated by Law 544/2001 on free access to information of public interest. In this regard, public and private institutions in our country are required to appoint a contact person for journalists and the general public, this person being a very important pillar and bears the title of spokesperson.

The peer-reviewed paper belongs to Ms. Roxana Popazu, MSc. student of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics, Politehnica University of Bucharest, who conducted a study upon completion of her Master's Degree and ultimately had to prepare her thesis. The research started from the work of theorists, to whom she exposed the ideas and then followed these theories and hypotheses with the research itself.

Thus, in 2022, she conducted a survey among communicators of the Ministry of Home Affairs to identify the communication characteristics of the

Ministry's spokespersons. The research findings reconfirm the existence of a close link between the personality type of the spokesperson and the communication style (Popazu, Roxana, 2022, p. 47).

In a context where communication plays a crucial role in the functioning of public institutions and in dealing with the public, the role of spokespersons is becoming increasingly important. These professionals have a responsibility to represent their organization and convey critical information to the public and the media.

Keywords: *spokesperson; institutional communication; public relations; charisma; social influence.*

Introduction - defining the concept of spokesperson. Role in reputation building.

“We live in a society that relays on information and communication, since they decidedly influence each of our daily activities” (Stănescu, 2016). In this context the role of the spokesperson in public institutions is extremely important.

The paper, *Public Relations and Media*, Coman, Cristina (2004, p. 89-93) provides information and a detailed description of the concept of spokesperson in the specialized literature, universally valid, and not only within a system where certain rules are applicable. This paper mentions the difference between the members of a press office and the designated spokesperson who, in addition to the usual tasks, has a set of specific duties for which special qualities are required.

By definition, the spokesperson takes the place of the leader of an organization in front of the media and must possess all the qualities and skills required of any other member of the press office, as well as public speaking experience and speed of reaction, important aspects that contribute to the sense of credibility they wish to convey to the public. (Ibid.)

The public relations literature argues that an effective spokesperson must demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of all aspects of the operations and strategies of the organization in which they are employed. It is imperative that the spokesperson is trusted by the management, as they are the organization's frontline in interacting with the public and the media. They must also be aware that their relationship with journalists needs to be one of collaboration and mutual respect. This is essential if information is to reach the public accurately, and in a context where "misinformation is a truly global threat" (Stănescu, 2020)

Another important goal is to build and maintain a positive organizational image. This entails the development and fostering of a coherent and authentic organizational identity. It also involves creating, developing and managing relationships with the media, analysts, influencers and other stakeholders.

Studies have further demonstrated that a positive image of the organization can significantly enhance its long-term success (Bromley et al., 2008, p. 255 - 261).

In *The Sociological Lens on Public Relations* (2009, p.147-148), Enache, Răzvan argues that nowadays not only do we as individuals want to control the impression we leave on those around us, but organizations also try to control how they are perceived, i.e., to manage their image.

In today's context, it has been found that public relations strategies are no longer exclusively about promoting an image in order to disguise reality. Rather, they have evolved towards a tendency to reveal, as opposed to hiding, the reality of an institution or organization.

Public campaigns, in the Romanian environment, are developed through strategies meant to inform and influence public choice, considering various methods and approaches to reconfigure interest groups within the public power structure. This approach is upheld by Adela Rogojinaru in her work *Public Relations: Interdisciplinary Foundations* (2005, p. 99). In the light of building image and trust in an institution, the author highlights that, although the main purpose is to cultivate trust, it is acknowledged that developing institutional image is still a significant focus in contemporary practice. Lesenciu, Adrian in *Theories of Communication*, (2017, p. 171-172) examines the impact of mass communication and, from a particular perspective, investigates research on interpersonal influence within groups. This approach leaves open the possibility of perceiving mass communication as a flow from individuals to their environment, in contrast to the traditional perspective that considers mass communication as a flow towards individuals.

Delving into the depth of understanding the concept of trust and being aware of the need to apply communication strategies developed on the basis of sociological research and feedback from citizens, Diana Maria Cismaru, in *Social Media and Reputation Management* (2012, p. 84), argues that trust implies that an entity is willing to expose itself to potential vulnerabilities in front of the actions of another entity, trusting

that the other entity will adopt a specific behavior of major importance with regard to the first entity, without questioning the latter's ability to control the situation.

The credibility and reputation of an organization, institution in the case of our study, is a key factor in developing trust in a relationship, and this dimension has been analyzed as a particularly important attribute for public sector actors in their interactions with different audiences.

Media can be seen as the means by which communication is achieved, in a context where information is conveyed and influence is exerted. The impact of communication is directly related to the ability of the spokesperson to use these tools effectively.

Research objectives/universe:

The study conducted and detailed in Roxana Popazu's thesis focused on identifying some of the communication characteristics of spokespersons within the Ministry of Home Affairs in our country in order to better understand how they influence organizational communication and their performance in this position.

The main objectives were to identify the specific communication styles of the studied group, the interplay between charisma, communication styles, personality traits and self-reported performance and, last but not least, the impact of charisma on communication style and performance.

With regard to the first objective of the study, through the evaluation of the data collected, various ways of communication adopted by the representatives of the Ministry of Home Affairs in their role as spokespersons were identified.

Subsequently, the research examined the connections between charisma, communication patterns, personal characteristics and subjective evaluations of spokesperson performance.

Also, for the third objective, an assessment of the influence of spokespersons' charisma on their communication methods and their performance in their role was conducted through data analysis.

The current research featured a cross-sectional design and involved the implementation of a set of assessment tools applied to a total of 63 spokespersons, out of which 22 were male and 44 females.

These individuals were selected to complete an online survey between 5 and 23 September 2022 using the Google Forms platform. The eligibility condition was the respondent's employment as a spokesperson for the Ministry of Home Affairs.

The sociodemographic data obtained from the survey included variables such as: (i) age of respondents; (ii) gender of respondents; (iii) level of experience; (iv) place of work in urban or rural areas; (v) employment sector (private or public); (vi) geographical region where spokespersons work.

The instruments used in this approach were the general charisma inventory composed of 6 items on a Likert-type scale, the communication styles inventory with 18 items in 3 subscales, the Big-Five-10 personality inventory and the performance self-assessment scale (Popazu, Roxana, p. 31-33).

Conclusions

As for the analysis of communication style, it can be seen that the highest average score is associated with the expressive style. With a significant probability, this can be considered the dominant style among the respondents. The expressive style is characterized by the propensity to communicate fluently, to initiate and steer conversations effortlessly, to display a sense of humor and to interact with others in a casual manner.

For the profession of spokesman, where effective interaction with the audience is of crucial importance, adopting an expressive communication style can indicate a rational attitude and a strong desire to be eloquent. This suggests that spokespersons tend to engage in communication with confidence, maintain an open and relaxed tone, and use humor to facilitate interpersonal relationships and ensure a deeper connection with their audience.

From the analysis, it can be seen that the respondent group, the MAI spokespersons, are distinguished by the presence of personality traits such as agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional balance and, to a significant extent, openness to new experiences. (Popazu, Roxana, p.36)

In terms of inward/outward orientation, the group exhibits rather ambivert characteristics, suggesting an inclination towards adaptability and the ability to fit successfully into a variety of social situations.

Regarding the correlation between charisma and communication styles, it was found that individuals with a high level of charisma tend to develop an expressive communication style, characterized by fluidity in conversation, easy wording of ideas, and use of humor to interact with others.

In contrast, a low level of charisma seems to be associated with a more emotional communication style, which may involve a more emotionally focused approach and communication that is more sensitive to the emotional reactions of others.

In research on leaders, analyses point to a correlation between the charisma variable and the importance attributed to trust, compassion and empathy, which are characteristics associated with kindness (according to Emery et al., 2013). In this context, in the analysis of spokespersons, charisma seems to emphasize more the dominance and consistency of the communication subject.

Observations on the study reiterate the role of charisma in influencing how individuals choose to express themselves and interact with others in the context of communication.

These conclusions can be a valuable starting point for the development of more effective communication strategies within the MAI and subordinate structures. The findings can also provide a more detailed insight into the elements that influence the success of a spokesperson and can also provide significant guidance for the further development and training of future spokespersons, but also "in the context of the appearance of new technologies such as metaverse." (Vlăduțescu&Stănescu, 2023)

Based on the theories identified in the specialized literature and on the findings of the reviewed study, I chose to develop the hypotheses and to carry out a more pragmatic analysis of the communication process implemented by the employees of the press structures of the Ministry of Home Affairs. Specifically, the study that is currently in progress has a target of 200 respondents, and the hypothesis is that the method of communication used by press officers and spokespersons influences the perception of the population and has a direct impact on the population's trust towards the MAI and its subordinate structures.

The eligibility criteria for research participants are to work in the press structures of the MAI, both in the central body as well as in the territorial, county or regional structures, such as the Border Police or the Coast Guard.

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